

EXPERIENCE OF CERTAIN STATES IN THE PREVENTION OF HARASSMENT AND VIOLENCE AGAINST WOMEN

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16718205>

Abstract

This article analyzes international practices in preventing violence against women and explores their potential adaptation within Uzbekistan's socio-legal framework. It examines legislative measures, institutional protection mechanisms, and prevention strategies from countries such as Australia, Spain, Canada, Turkey, Japan, Norway, Switzerland, and India, including protection orders, awareness campaigns, mobile applications, and electronic monitoring. The study also reviews current initiatives in Uzbekistan such as protective orders, rehabilitation centers, and civil society involvement. The article concludes with evidence-based recommendations for the gradual integration of international approaches aligned with national cultural and legal contexts.

Keywords: Violence against women, international practice, prevention program, protection order, electronic monitoring, mobile applications, gender equality, rehabilitation center, psychological support, legal mechanisms

Pressure and violence against women is one of the most widespread problems on a global scale. This disease poses a serious threat not only to personal life, but also to social stability, human rights, and development. According to the United Nations, every third woman in the world experiences physical or psychological violence at least once in her life.[1] Below, the best practices of some foreign countries in this area are analyzed, and the possibilities of their application in accordance with the conditions of Uzbekistan are studied. First of all, if we dwell on international legislative acts, the "Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women" (CEDAW - Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women) is an international convention of the United Nations Organization. This document guarantees the elimination of any forms of discrimination against women, ensuring their equal rights and opportunities with men in the political, social, economic, and cultural spheres. Every state that has adopted this international convention is obligated to include in its Constitution and laws clauses protecting the rights of women. This international convention closely links gender equality in the legislation of all states. Today, the Strategic Concept for Increasing Gender Equality of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030 also puts forward issues of training reserve personnel in order to ensure women's participation in society and appoint them to leadership positions. On the basis of the Resolution of the Senate of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Improving the Activities of the Senate of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Comprehensive Support for Women and Ensuring Gender Equality," the Committee on Women's and Gender Equality Issues was created. Women of Uzbekistan constitute more than 51 percent of the country's population, of which: in higher parliamentary activity - 30% senators; women

deputies - 32%; in local Kengashes - 25% women deputies; In the Ministry of Internal Affairs - 16 women leaders; khokims of regions, districts and cities - 7 people; in addition, in the context of various organizations (entrepreneurship, agriculture, etc.) - 1,500 female leaders are working. In Uzbekistan, concepts such as "gender equality," "family violence," and "protection order" have become increasingly common. Their similarity lies in the fact that these concepts are mainly applied to women who have fallen into difficult life situations and have been subjected to violence in the family. According to statistics, Uzbekistan ranks 57th in the "Gender Inequality Index" ranking.

Laws and programs developed at the state level to ensure gender equality are also of great importance. Even according to the results of a study conducted by the World Economic Forum, women work almost 35 days more per year than men. According to the UN Children's Fund (UNICEF), girls spend 35-36 percent more time doing any work compared to boys. This shows that gender equality is still not being achieved in the world. [5]

Since ancient times, in human society, the family, family relations, the role and duties of husband and wife in the family, as well as the norms of family management and regulation of relations have always been at the center of attention of the state, the general public, in particular, scientists, and have been the subject of discussions and debates in religious circles. Ancient Greek scholars such as Socrates, Aristotle, and Plato also promoted the idea of a "polis" where equality and justice prevail as the best state, advocating for the inclusion of norms guaranteeing the principles of equality in the law. Eastern encyclopedic scholar Abu Nasr Farabi, in his work "The City of Virtuous People," noted that a state where equality reigns as a state striving for virtue,[6] and in 1791, Olimpiya De Guj's "Declaration of Citizenship and Women's Rights" recognized for the first time that women have the right to freely think and express their opinions.[7]

Prevention of harassment and violence against women is relevant in all countries. As proof of this, we will dwell on what penalties are established for such crimes in the legislation of some countries.

Francea "In difficult cases for domestic violence, there is a punishment of imprisonment from 3 to 10 years." "Sexual assault or rape - up to 15 years in prison (up to 20 years for minors)." There is a separate law for psychological pressure (since 2010); regular psychological pressure is also considered a crime. "Qurbonni ta'qib qilish" (harassment, "harcèlement") - 1 year in prison or a fine of up to 15 thousand euros.

In Germany and "Rape or sexual assault for 1 to 15 years." "In cases of domestic violence, to ensure the safety of the victim, the temporary eviction of the offender is under the authority of the police." Sud himoya orderi (Schutzanordnung) chiqaradi. There is also criminal liability for psychological pressure.[9]

In the United States of America based on federal and state laws, penalties for domestic violence vary by state - from 1 to 20 years imprisonment. In cases of sexual assault, life imprisonment is also applied. Courts issue protection orders (restraining order). Cases of psychological and economic violence are also considered crimes in some states.[10]

In Great Britain actions based on physical, mental, financial and control are recognized as violence. Punishments for violence - imprisonment for 5 to 14 years. The court issues protection orders: "Non-Molestation Order" or "Occupation Order." "Coercive control" is punishable by up to 5 years in prison for compulsory control (mental pressure).[11]

In India "Harsh treatment of his wife" - imprisonment and fine for up to 3 years. Protection of the victim, temporary shelters and assistance services have been established. Sexual violence, psychological pressure, economic restrictions are also within the scope of the law.[12]

Sweden implements a strict policy against gender-based violence. Rape is punishable by a minimum of 2 years, and in severe cases, by more than 10 years of imprisonment. Since 2018, the law "Sexual intercourse based on consent" has been considered a crime if there is no open consent of the victim. Maishiy z'yravonlik - ruhiy yoki jismoniy b'olsin - jinoiy javobgarlikka olib keladi. In primary and secondary schools, lessons on gender equality and the culture of relationships have been introduced as mandatory. Every year in Sweden, mass campaigns are organized under the slogans "Moderate masculinity" and "Zooanlikka nol chidash." [13]

In Switzerland however, shelter centers are called frauenhaus. In 2018, a total of 1,771 cases of domestic violence were reported in 19 women's shelter centers across the country, of which 487 were rejected due to a lack of accommodation or staff. Another 319 were not admitted to shelters for other reasons. Almost half of all applications were rejected, and 41 percent of these women found a place in other crisis centers. the remaining 965 women in 19 shelters had an average stay of 37 days.[14]

The state of pressure and violence against women is also one of the main social problems **for Argentina**. In January-June 2022, a total of 63,202 appeals were received through three means (telephone, WhatsApp, and e-mail) to the 144 line (Linea 144) service, 91 percent of which were within the framework of family relations. Compared to the corresponding period of 2021, the number of cases of violence increased by 11,117. In 94 percent of cases, psychological, in 64 percent of cases, physical, in 41 percent of cases, economic, in 14 percent of cases, sexual violence was committed, and in 13 percent of cases, weapons or other means were used. In 97% of cases of violence, the victims are women, and in 87 cases, the perpetrators are men.

An interactive violence map of the city of Buenos Aires, the capital of the country, has been developed, reflecting the cases of harassment and violence committed in 2021, which provides information on which communes (communes - administrative units) of the city have the best results in the commission of violence, which type of violence is more common in which communes, an analysis of violence by month, which state's citizens it was committed against, and what measures were taken. **In Canada**, there are also problems related to the protection of women and their children subjected to harassment and violence. For example, 80 percent of victims of domestic violence who apply to shelters for women receive a rejection. According to the results of the study in November 2019, an average of 620 women and their children who experienced harassment and violence received a rejection in one day. This means that almost 19,000 women per month cannot be accommodated in the centers. The main reason for this is the lack of space in these shelters. In the 2020/2021 fiscal year, a total of 43,729 victims of violence applied to more than 500 centers and shelters **in Canada**, of which 26,736 (61.1%) were women and 16,575 (37.9%) were children. In most cases, the appeals of women and children to shelters are explained by the fact that they have encountered cases of family, sexual, psychological, financial violence and harassment.

In Australia, measures are being implemented to prevent cases of harassment and violence against women, aimed at social protection and categories requiring special attention.

In particular: In preventing cases of violence against women in Australia, attention is paid to the peculiarities of their age periods: aspects of violence against juvenile girls, adult women, and elderly women are distinguished;

Attention will be paid to eliminating cases of violence against women with disabilities. In 2019, people with disabilities in Australia experienced 1.7 times more sexual violence after 15 years compared to healthy people; [18] Migrant and refugee women and their children, culturally belonging to other groups, are also classified as a separate risk group. System of Interaction of Organizations in Preventing Violence.

Prevention of harassment and violence, comprehensive support for women who have become victims of violence requires cooperation between existing state and non-state organizations in the country. The system of cooperation in this area is unique for each state, and we will briefly dwell on each of them.

In Switzerland the following state and non-state organizations cooperate to protect women who have been subjected to harassment and violence: [19] Civil Court; Agencies for Working with Victims; Police; Social security bodies; Legal advisory bodies for migrant women; Healthcare institutions; Maktablar; Preschool educational institutions and others.

In Singapore, a system of cooperation between state and non-state organizations has been established to support and rehabilitate victims of harassment and violence. Family courts, family service centers, police, hospitals, educational institutions, and social service agencies will cooperate to support women facing violence. Within the structure of the Ministry of Social and Family Development, the Adult Protective Service (APS) - that is, the "Adult Protection Service" - has been introduced, and [20] this structure operates in two directions:

1. Controls organizations providing assistance to persons in need of social protection, who have encountered domestic violence, coordinates the work on referring such persons to the relevant services, ensuring their safety;

2. Strategic partner organizations for the protection of persons subjected to violence - police, hospitals, social service agencies, family courts and Academic Research in Educational Multidisciplinary Scientific Journal control activities, develop a general strategy. APS also improves the professional qualifications of specialists working with individuals subjected to harassment and violence.

In Argentina The National Action Plan against Gender-Based Violence for 2022-2024 has been adopted, which includes 100 short-term, medium-term and long-term actions of 20 ministries and 5 national agencies. The National Action Plan establishes cooperation between ministries, federal and municipal authorities. Within the framework of the Action Plan, it is planned to allocate: a 6-month allowance in the amount of the minimum wage for women who have been subjected to violence; subsidies in the amount of 47 to 70 times the minimum wage for legal entities to support women who have been subjected to gender violence; and for individuals - in the amount of 23 times the minimum wage. [21]

In Argentina, the system of cooperation to prevent violence against women and support women is coordinated by the National Women's Council, and the Council and the Ministry of Women, Gender and Diversity are the authorized bodies. The cooperation system also includes the National Council for Minors and Family Affairs (coordinates state and private services for women who have become victims of harassment and violence), the court, the Ministry of Social Development, the Ministry of Justice (maintains a register of centers

providing free legal assistance), the Ministry of Public Education, healthcare institutions (provides free first aid), the Observatory for Violence against Women (studies the causes of cases of violence, analyzes the problem from a scientific point of view), non-governmental non-profit organizations, the specialized police corps (works with offenses related to women and committed against women), municipal authorities, the bar, and trade unions

Japan According to Article 2.2 of the Law No. 31 "On Prevention of Domestic Violence and Protection of Victims," adopted by the Parliament of Japan on April 13, 2001, the Prime Minister, the National Public Safety Commission, the Ministry of Justice, and the Ministry of Health, Labor, and Well-being implement the main state policy in the area of preventing domestic violence.[22] The cooperation system also includes prefectures and municipal administrations, advisory and assistance centers on domestic violence, police, healthcare institutions, social assistance organizations, courts, and non-governmental organizations. On October 17, 2022, the National Plan for the Elimination of Violence against Women and Children for 2022-2032 was announced, and this National Plan was adopted by the state and federal government. The National Plan establishes cooperation between all state and non-state organizations of society - government, business entities, mass media, schools and educational institutions, organizations fighting against family, domestic and sexual violence, and others. It is planned that the National Plan will include two five-year plans. The main goal of the National Plan is to eradicate any form of violence against women and children. The Commission on Family, Domestic, and Sexual Violence (CSV) will coordinate the work carried out within the framework of the National Plan and submit an annual report to the parliament.

In **Canada**, when supporting women who have become victims of violence, the main focus is on restoring their health and mental state. In general, within the framework of the interdepartmental program, such federal bodies as the Ministry of Health, the Prosecutor General's Office, the Ministry of Justice, the Ministry of Women and Gender Equality, the Royal Canadian Police, regional and provincial governments, ministries, NGOs and centers, charitable organizations, educational institutions, the legal profession, and other state and non-state organizations operate in the country. Legislative system on harassment and violence. Every country's legislative system is unique. The system of legislation on violence is also a part of the existing legal norm-making system in the country. In some countries, legislation is single-tiered (Singapore, Japan), while in others, there are federal and territorial legislative institutions (Canada, Australia, Switzerland).

Singapore Part 7, Articles 64-67 of the "Women's Charter," adopted by the Parliament of the Republic of **Singapore** on September 15, 1961, are titled "Family Protection." The Charter provides an explanation of the concept of family violence. Article 65 of the Charter establishes the procedure for issuing a protection order by the court in the event of violence. Yulduz: Zaruriyat tu'g'ilganda sud bir kun ichida qisqa muddatli (28 kun) himoya orderi berishi tizimi ishlab chiqilgan (Article 66).[23] Also, based on Canadian experience, the "Strategy to Prevent and Address Gender-Based Violence" was adopted in Canada in 2017. It is aimed at eliminating the root causes of violence, eradicating wrong gender roles in society. Prevention is carried out not only with the participation of the state, but also with the participation of civil society and the private sector. For example, large companies like McDonald's, CBC, Bell implement corporate programs against violence for their employees.

Since **Switzerland** is a confederation by form of government, federal laws for the whole country are adopted by the country's parliament, i.e., the Federal Council of the Swiss

Confederation. The Federal Law "On Providing Assistance to Victims of Crime," adopted on October 4, 1991 (re-adopted on March 23, 2007), provides a legal assessment of the issue of providing assistance to women subjected to harassment and violence. According to the Swiss Criminal Code adopted on December 21, 1937, domestic violence is grounds for criminal prosecution.[25] Pressure and violence against women in various forms are classified as crimes. **In Argentina** a strong regulatory and legal system for protecting women from violence has been created. In particular, the Argentine National Congress adopted national laws "On Protection against Family Violence" No. 24.417 of December 28, 1994, and "On Comprehensive Protection of Women" No. 26.485 of March 11, 2009. The concepts of "family violence" and "violence against women" have been introduced into Argentine legislation. **Japanese** Parliament Article 1 of the Law No. 31 "On Prevention of Family Violence and Protection of Victims," adopted on April 13, 2001, defines the concept of "family violence" (or "violence between husband and wife"). In this case, the commission of violence in cases of family separation and legal marriage is also interpreted as family violence.[22]

In Australia the system of legislation on harassment and violence is formed on the basis of federal, state laws, and court decisions. The Federal Law No. 53,1975 "On Family Law," adopted by the Federal Parliament of Australia on June 12, 1975, and amended 84 times[28], as well as the Federal Law No. 189,2011 "On Amendments to Legislation on Family Law (Family Violence and Other Measures) " adopted on December 7, 2011,[29] define the main legal directions for combating and preventing cases of violence in the country.

In Spain The "Gender-Based Violence Protection Act" (Ley Orgánica 1/2004) adopted in 2004 created a fundamental turning point in the fight against gender violence in Spain. Within the framework of this law, special courts have been established, and cases of violence are resolved through a comprehensive approach in the legal, medical, social, and educational spheres. If he approaches the victim from the specified distance, the police and the victim will be notified automatically. At the same time, victims of violence are provided with special housing, material assistance, and assistance in employment.[31]

Research methods: In conducting the research on this topic, the experience of some countries in the prevention of harassment and violence against women, as well as the role of crime, were used. An attempt was made to identify modern problems and their solutions by studying legal and economic literature, conducting a comparative-critical analysis of official statistical data, and analyzing the opinions of scholars. In the analysis process, classical scientific methods such as comparative analysis, generalization, comparison, synthesis, and analysis were effectively used.

Muhokama. If we consider the social compatibility of the above-mentioned experience of some foreign countries using the example of the Republic of Uzbekistan, let's take a preventive program aimed at changing public consciousness based on the experience of Australia. **In Australia** Through the "Our Watch" program, education about healthy relationships is conducted in schools, workplaces, and universities. This program yielded successful results and sharply reduced instances of violence. Media control over the promotion of sexual and gender-based violence has been strengthened. Restrictions have been imposed on the portrayal of violence as "romantic" or "worthy" behavior on television, film, and social media.[32]

This "Our Watch" program, adapted to Uzbekistan, can be implemented in stages through legal foundations, social consciousness, education system, and mass media. In this

process, the following practical steps are proposed: Implementation of mandatory training modules on healthy relationships in schools and universities; Creation of a media monitoring system (controlling against the "romantication" or habitualization of violence); Creation of culturally appropriate programs for changing gender consciousness with the involvement of religious and mahalla leaders.

Ispaniya, Turkiya, Kanada davlatlari misolidagi shaxsiy himoya orderi yoki himoyalovchi sud qarorlariga keladigan bo'lsak, sud qarori asosida zo'ravon shaxsga qurbonga yaqinlashish, uni bezovta qilish, telefon qilish, yashash manzilisiga borish taqiqlanadi. This experience is already an existing system of protection orders in the Republic of Uzbekistan, which can be strengthened and automated in accordance with world experience. The issuance of protection orders through courts has been simplified, implemented in an expedited manner, even in electronic form.

Spain and France Based on preventive methods, electronic control devices - a bracelet and a monitoring system are worn by the abuser based on a court decision, and the police automatically receive a signal when he approaches the victim. The introduction of such technologies in the Republic of Uzbekistan may be implemented as a pilot project by the Ministry of Internal Affairs and the justice system. This system can have a strong psychological and legal impact.

In the experience of countries such as **Turkey (KADES), India (MySafetipin), Argentina (144 App)** there are mobile applications for quick assistance: the victim applies to police assistance in real time. In Uzbekistan, mobile applications such as "Minvoda" or "MySafety.uz" can be developed. At the same time, there is a mobile application "SOS", which is intended not only for women, but also for lonely elderly people, disabled people, and other needy groups. Special shelters and service centers in countries **such as the Netherlands, Germany, and the USA** offer victims of violence free accommodation, psychological assistance, legal advice, and rehabilitation programs. Such shelters exist in the Republic of Uzbekistan, and in order to improve the social rehabilitation system, the Republican Center for Rehabilitation and Adaptation of Victims of Violence was established by Presidential Decree of July 2, 2018. Currently, 197 such centers operate in the country. **PRACTICAL RESULTS.** Main tasks of these centers:

- providing emergency medical, psychological, social, pedagogical, legal, and other assistance anonymously to women who have suffered from harassment and violence, who have committed suicide, or who are prone to suicide;
- Assistance in ensuring guarantees of the rights of women in difficult social situations, including those who have encountered family problems and violence in their lives;
 - studying cases of suicide and assassination of women by state bodies and civil society institutions, preventing such cases, as well as closely assisting in the activities of women who have committed suicide to return to normal life;
 - **Take measures to comprehensively support and remove from the "Women's Notebook" women in need of psychological and legal counseling (women who are victims of harassment and violence, women with social problems) and [other.](#)**

Compulsory rehabilitation programs for violators - based on the experience of **Norway** According to the experience of Norway, violators are involved in compulsory psychological therapy courses, programs aimed at reforming their personality and culture of relationships

are implemented. In the context of Uzbekistan, this process can be carried out by court decision or at the initiative of internal affairs bodies, as well as mechanisms of social influence with the participation of mahalla activists and religious scholars. Gender-based statistical monitoring - based on the experience of Sweden, Finland and the USA. In these countries, cases of violence against women are regularly subjected to statistical analysis through a digital monitoring system. In Uzbekistan, this experience can be implemented jointly with the Statistics Agency and the Women's Committee. Through open statistical data provided to the public quarterly, public trust and monitoring of the issue are strengthened.

Adaptability in labor relations - based on European experience. It is proposed to introduce a flexible work regime in enterprises and organizations, especially for pregnant women, single mothers, or women raising children, and to implement remote work, reduced working hours, or online forms of activity. This approach ensures that employees work without hindering their family responsibilities while maintaining their qualifications. This mechanism is currently widely used in **Russia and** European countries.

Conclusion. The effectiveness of the fight against violence against women in the context of foreign experience and Uzbekistan depends on the following complex factors

Strength of the legal basis (protection orders, specific norms introduced into the Criminal Code); Preventive education and media control (school, media, changing consciousness through religious teachings); Special services (shelters, rehabilitation centers, emergency aid applications); Electronic technologies and automated control systems (bilaguzuk, GPS-monitoring); Active participation of the public and civil society (NGOs, the legal profession, trade unions);

Creating flexible working conditions in organizations (maintaining the productivity of women's labor). International experience shows that the introduction of the topic of healthy relationships into the education system, the overcoming of gender stereotypes, the use of information technologies, and close cooperation between the state and society play an important role in preventing violence. In Uzbekistan, by implementing these mechanisms step by step, adapted to the national mentality, it is possible to further strengthen the system of protecting women.

Used literature//Footnotes/References:

1. World Health Organization (WHO). (2021). Violence against women prevalence estimates, 2018. Geneva: WHO. Retrieved from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240022256>
2. United Nations. (1979). Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women (CEDAW). UN General Assembly. Retrieved from: <https://www.un.org/womenwatch/daw/cedaw/>
3. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan. (December 29, 1995). Law "On International Treaties of the Republic of Uzbekistan."
4. Collection of materials of the international scientific and practical conference "The Role of Women in the Development of Science and Gender Equality in Renewed Uzbekistan." Tashkent, 2021.

5. Materials of the Republican Scientific and Practical Conference "Gender Equality in Family-Legal Relations." Research Institute of Mahalla and Family. Tashkent, 2021.
6. Abu Nasr Forobiy. Fozil odamlar shahri. (Original source: Arabic. Based on the translation into Uzbek)
7. Olimpia de Guj. Declaration of Women's and Civil Rights. France, 1791.
8. French Criminal Code. Articles: 222-22, 222-23, 222-24. <https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr>
9. Germany's Criminal Code (Strafgesetzbuch - StGB). Articles: 177-241. https://www.gesetze-im-internet.de/englisch_stgb/
10. United States Federal Law. Office on Violence Against Women. U.S. Department of Justice. <https://www.justice.gov/ovw>
11. United Kingdom Government. (2021). Domestic Abuse Act 2021. <https://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2021/17/contents/enacted>
12. Indian Criminal Code. Article 498A. <https://indiacode.nic.in>
13. Shvetsiya Jinoyat Kodeksi (Brottsbalken), Chapter 6: Jinsiy huquqbuzarliklar. <https://www.government.se>
14. SwissInfo.ch. (2019). Shelters for victims of domestic violence struggle with capacity issues. Retrieved from: https://www.swissinfo.ch/eng/society/violence-against-women_shelters-for-victims-of-domestic-violence-struggle-with-capacity-issues/44957702
15. Argentina Government - Línea 144. (2022). <https://www.argentina.gob.ar/generos/linea-144/datos-publicos-de-la-linea-144-2022> Statistics Canada. (2022). Table 4 - Victims of intimate partner violence reported by police. <https://www150.statcan.gc.ca/> Heidinger, L. (2021). Intimate partner violence: Experiences of First Nations, Métis and Inuit women in Canada, 2018. Juristat, Canadian Centre for Justice Statistics.
18. Australian Institute of Health and Welfare (AIHW). (2019). Family, domestic and sexual violence in Australia: continuing the national story. <https://www.aihw.gov.au>
19. Frauenhaus Basel (Switzerland): <https://frauenhaus-basel.ch/frauenhaus>
20. Adult Protection Service – Singapore <https://www.msf.gov.sg/about-MSF/our-people/Divisions-at-MSF/Social-Development-and-Support/Rehabilitation-and-Protection-Group/Adult-ProtectiveService/Pages/default.aspx>
21. Argentina - National Action Plan 2022-2024. https://www.argentina.gob.ar/sites/default/files/2022/08/pna_2022_2024.pdf
22. Japan - Gender Equality Bureau. Law on the Prevention of Marital Violence and the Protection of Victims. https://www.gender.go.jp/policy/no_violence/e-vaw/law/pdf/nichiei.pdf

